

CONFIDENCE AND ACTUAL ABILITY IN IDENTIFYING FAKE NEWS: A DESCRIPTIVE CORRELATIONAL STUDY

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to determine the level of confidence and actual ability of the students in identifying fake news and to examine the relationship between these variables and correlational design and employed the stratified random sampling technique. The respondents of the study were the 314 freshmen students from the ten colleges of Foundation University, Dumaguete City, during the Academic Year 2025–2026. The researcher used a researcher-made and expert-validated questionnaire and employed weighted mean and Spearman's Rank Order Correlation Coefficient for the statistical treatment of data. The findings revealed that the students exhibited a high level of confidence yet demonstrated a low to very low level of actual ability in identifying fake news, particularly in recognizing disinformation. Results further showed a very weak negative significant relationship between confidence and actual ability in disinformation, while no significant relationships were found in misinformation and malinformation. These findings imply that although students express strong confidence in their ability to detect false information, their actual evaluative competence remains limited, emphasizing the importance of strengthening media and information literacy.

Keywords: *actual ability, confidence, disinformation, misinformation, malinformation, media and information literacy*

INTRODUCTION

The rapid spread of fake news on social media has become a global concern, misleading communities, disrupting democratic processes, and weakening trust in institutions

(Gupta et al., 2022; Hassain, 2022; Pérez-Escoda, 2022). Youth are particularly vulnerable because they rely heavily on digital platforms and often overestimate their ability to identify fake news, which creates a false sense of competence (Syam & Nurrahmi, 2020; Al Zou'bi, 2022; Martínez-Costa et al., 2022). International studies consistently show a complex and often weak relationship between confidence and actual ability to detect fake news, frequently marked by overconfidence (Corbu et al., 2020; Weiss et al., 2020; Dabbous et al., 2021; Lan & Tung, 2024). However, this relationship remains underexplored in the Philippine context, where social media plays a central role in everyday life.

In the Philippines, fake news is particularly prevalent in political discourse. Studies indicate that political polarization and echo chambers increase Filipino youth's susceptibility to misinformation while fostering distrust in traditional news sources (Deinla et al., 2022). Disinformation campaigns also exploit cultural narratives, making audiences more receptive to false content (Cabañes & Santiago, 2023). Although students often claim familiarity with fake news, research shows persistent weaknesses in digital literacy skills such as author and fact checking (Linsangan et al., 2021; Fajardo, 2023). The COVID-19 "infodemic" further illustrated this gap, as young adults in Cebu displayed confidence in recognizing misinformation yet lacked the critical prosuming (producing and consuming) skills needed for consistent accuracy (Maningo et al., 2022).

Despite growing global and local literature, few studies have specifically examined the relationship between confidence and actual ability to detect fake news among Filipino freshmen students. This group is especially important, as they are highly active online and are transitioning into higher education. Addressing this gap is crucial, since misaligned confidence and actual ability can weaken students' resilience to fake news and affect informed decision-making.

This study responds to this gap by examining the relationship between freshmen's confidence and their actual ability to identify fake news. The findings aim to inform targeted media literacy interventions that align confidence with competence. Moreover, the study supports the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals, particularly SDG 4 (Quality Education) and SDG 16 (Peace, Justice, and Strong Institutions), by promoting critical engagement with reliable information. By addressing an often-overlooked aspect of the fake news problem in the Philippines, the study fills a scholarly gap while also contributing to practical, societal, and developmental goals.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the relationship between confidence and actual ability in identifying fake news among freshmen students at Foundation University.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of freshmen students' confidence in identifying fake news as classified according to:

- 1.1. misinformation;
 - 1.2. disinformation; and
 - 1.3. malinformation?
2. What is the level of freshmen students' actual ability in identifying fakes news as classified according to:
 - 2.1. misinformation;
 - 2.2. disinformation; and
 - 2.3. malinformation?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study utilizes a descriptive correlational research design, which is appropriate for examining the relationship between students perceived confidence and their actual ability to identify fake news. It also investigates whether the number of hours spent daily on social media significantly influences these variables. The correlational design is suitable because it measures existing relationships without manipulating the environment, allowing the study of naturally occurring behaviors among students.

Research Locale

This study was conducted at Foundation University, a private, non-sectarian institution of higher learning in Dumaguete City, Negros Oriental. Established in 1949, the university has been recognized for its commitment to academic excellence, innovation, and social responsibility. The study will also take place within the broader context of Dumaguete City, known as the "City of Gentle People" and widely regarded as a university town in the Visayas region. The campus setting provides a suitable environment for gathering data, as it represents a diverse population of first-year students from different programs and backgrounds.

Research Respondents

The respondents of this study are the freshmen students of Foundation University, Dumaguete City, for the School Year 2025–2026. The total number of freshmen enrolled across the ten colleges of the university is 1,436. Using Yamane's formula with a 5% margin of error, the computed sample size is 314 respondents. Respondents were selected through stratified random sampling by college to ensure proportional and fair representation. Data collection was conducted at Foundation University for accessibility and convenience, with equitable participation across programs. The distribution of respondents per college is shown below.

Research Instrument

The main data-gathering tool is a researcher-made questionnaire with four parts: Part I provides the disclosure statement, Part II collects respondent profiles, Part III measures

perceived confidence in identifying fake news, and Part IV assesses actual ability regarding misinformation, disinformation, and malinformation. The questionnaire was reviewed by experts for clarity and appropriateness, revised accordingly, and pilot-tested on 30 non-participant students. Its reliability was evaluated using Cronbach's Alpha, with scores interpreted following George and Mallery (2003).

Indicators	No. of Items	Cronbach Alpha	Interpretation
Misinformation	5	0.8049	Good
Disinformation	5	0.8529	Good
Malinformation	5	0.7698	Acceptable

Data Gathering Procedure

After the design hearing, all panel recommendations were incorporated and formal approval to conduct the study was secured from Foundation University. The researcher coordinated with college administrators and teachers, and the questionnaires underwent expert validation and pilot testing to ensure reliability and appropriateness. The refined questionnaires were then personally administered by the researcher in classrooms, where the study's purpose was clearly explained and respondents were assured of voluntary participation and strict confidentiality. Completed questionnaires were collected immediately, encoded using MS Excel, and analyzed through JAMOVI using descriptive and inferential statistics to address the research questions.

Questionnaires were completed on the spot and collected immediately to ensure a high response rate. The data were organized and encoded in MS Excel, then analyzed using JAMOVI with both descriptive and inferential statistics to examine the relationship between perceived confidence, and actual ability.

Statistical Tools

The researchers utilized the mean and standard deviation in analyzing the gathered data. The mean was used to measure both the respondent's confidence and actual ability in identifying fake news. Meanwhile, the standard deviation was computed to determine the degree of variation or dispersion of the respondents' scores from the mean.

RESULTS

Table 1.1
Confidence In identifying Misinformation (n=314)

Indicators	mean	SD	VD	LOP
1. When an online page shares old news and presents it as something recent.	3.83	0.94	A	H
2. When a celebrity or influencer shares news or opinions about a public issue.	3.89	0.87	A	H

3. If a rumor or trending topic spreads quickly online.	3.90	0.91	A	H
4. When I come across posts using statistics or data to support an argument.	3.77	0.94	A	H
5. When I read posts about health remedies or diet trends.	3.91	0.91	A	H
Composite	3.86	0.92	A	H

Note: Verbal Description (VD); Level of perception (LOP); 4.21-5.00, Strongly Agree (SA), Very High (VH); 3.41-4.20, Agree (A), High (H); 2.61-3.40, Moderately Agree (MA), Moderate (M); 1.81-2.60, Disagree (D), Low (L); 1.00-1.80, Strongly Disagree (SD), Very Low (VL)

Table 1.1 shows that respondents generally have a high level of confidence in identifying misinformation, with a composite mean of 3.86, interpreted as Agree and described as High. The highest mean (3.91) is observed for the indicator measuring confidence in evaluating health remedies or diet trends, suggesting that respondents feel most capable of determining whether such advice is supported by trusted medical sources. In contrast, the lowest mean (3.77) is for verifying statistics or data used to support arguments, indicating that while respondents still feel confident in this area, they perceive it as slightly more challenging compared to other aspects of identifying misinformation.

Table 1.2
Confidence in Identifying Disinformation (n=314)

Indicators	mean	SD	VD	LOP
1. I am confident in my ability to recognize when fabricated news stories are strategically crafted to manipulate public discourse and sway collective opinion.	3.97	0.89	A	H
2. I can identify manipulated photos or videos that have been digitally altered, edited out of context, or intentionally misrepresented to deceive or influence viewers.	3.87	0.98	A	H
3. I feel confident in noticing fake social media accounts, pages, or online profiles that are created specifically to spread disinformation or promote biased narratives.	3.86	0.94	A	H
4. I can recognize when statistics or figures are intentionally exaggerated to make people believe a party's side.	3.80	0.96	A	H
5. I am able to discern when misleading information is circulated with the intent of advancing partisan interests or securing economic advantage.	3.80	1.00	A	H
Composite	3.88	0.94	A	H

Note: Verbal Description (VD); Level of perception (LOP); 4.21-5.00, Strongly Agree (SA), Very High (VH); 3.41-4.20, Agree (A), High (H); 2.61-3.40, Moderately Agree (MA), Moderate (M); 1.81-2.60, Disagree (D), Low (L); 1.00-1.80, Strongly Disagree (SD), Very Low (VL)

Table 1.2 shows that respondents have the highest confidence in recognizing fabricated news stories strategically crafted to manipulate public opinion (mean = 3.97, SD = 0.89), indicating strong awareness of deliberate misinformation. The lowest confidence, though still high, is in detecting exaggerated statistics and information circulated for partisan or economic purposes (mean = 3.80, SD = 0.96–1.00), suggesting that respondents find subtle or data-driven disinformation slightly more challenging to identify. Overall, the table indicates that respondents feel generally capable of identifying disinformation, with

greater confidence in spotting overtly fabricated content than in discerning nuanced manipulations.

Table 1.3
Confidence in Identifying Malinformation (n=314)

Indicators	mean	SD	VD	LOP
1. I feel confident in recognizing when true information is twisted to damage someone’s reputation.	4.04	0.83	A	H
2. I can detect when a quotation is presented without its original context to make someone’s narrative a negative one.	3.90	0.87	A	H
3. I can identify when personal or private details are shared online to harm someone.	4	0.86	A	H
4. I feel confident in spotting when facts are selectively used to misrepresent a statement.	3.93	0.87	A	H
5. I can recognize when sensitive but true information is spread to embarrass others.	4.02	0.89	A	H
Composite	3.98	0.86	A	H

Note: Verbal Description (VD); Level of perception (LOP); 4.21-5.00, Strongly Agree (SA), Very High (VH); 3.41-4.20, Agree (A), High (H); 2.61-3.40, Moderately Agree (MA), Moderate (M); 1.81-2.60, Disagree (D), Low (L); 1.00-1.80, Strongly Disagree (SD), Very Low (VL)

Table 1.3 shows that respondents exhibit high confidence in identifying malinformation, with a composite mean of 3.98 (SD = 0.86). The highest confidence is in recognizing when true information is twisted to damage someone’s reputation (mean = 4.04), indicating respondents feel most capable of detecting reputational harm. The lowest confidence is in detecting when a quotation is presented out of context to create a negative narrative (mean = 3.90), though it still reflects a high level of perception. Overall, respondents perceive themselves as able to identify malinformation effectively.

Table 2.1
Actual Ability in Identifying Misinformation (n=314)

Item Statement	Correct Answer	
	f	%
1. House Approves P6-Trillion 2026 Proposed National Budget; DOF, DEPDev, DBM Budgets Reviewed (Net25, September 25, 2025)	203	65%
2. DepEd, CHED, TESDA Partner With OPAPRU to Strengthen Peace Education Programs (HiritPH)	98	31%
3. Cayetano Urges Judiciary’s Role in Building a Culture of Integrity (Statement of Sen. Alan Peter Cayetano)	131	42%
4. VP Sara Duterte Says ‘Third Country’ Open to Hosting Former President Duterte if ICC Grants Interim Release (Statement of Vice President Sara Duterte)	110	35%

5. ICC Releases Redacted Charges Document Against Former President Rodrigo Duterte (ABS-CBN News, September 23, 2025) 194 62%

Mean = 2.36 (Low Ability)

Note: Frequency (f); Percentage (%); Level of Ability; 5 - Very High Ability; 4 - High Ability; 3 - Moderate Ability; 2- Low Ability; 0-1 - Very Low Ability

In Table 2.1, respondents showed the highest actual ability in identifying the statement about the “House Approves P6-Trillion 2026 Proposed National Budget” with 65% answering correctly, indicating better recognition of widely reported government news. The lowest ability was observed in identifying the “DepEd, CHED, TESDA Partner With OPAPRU to Strengthen Peace Education Programs” item, with only 31% correct, suggesting difficulty in verifying less prominent or specialized news. Overall, the mean score of 2.36 reflects a low level of actual ability, indicating that while respondents may feel confident, their performance in accurately identifying misinformation is limited.

Table 2.2
Actual Ability in Identifying Disinformation (n=314)

Item Statement	Correct Answer	
	f	%
1. Dela Rosa Questions Marcos Administration’s Alleged Service to Foreign Interests (Video by Jesse Bustos / The Philippine STAR, March 25, 2025)	137	44%
2. Sara Duterte Labels Marcos Administration as ‘Face of Corruption and Abuse’ (Manila Bulletin, September 21, 2025)	88	28%
3. Pulong Duterte Criticizes Makabayan Bloc’s Claim of Nationalist Representation (Gikan sa Masa Para sa Masa)	100	32%
4. Conflicting Narratives Emerge Amid Flood Control Corruption Controversy (Usapang Totoo Lang)	210	67%
5. Wency Cornejo Raises Questions Following Plunder Charges vs. Duterte and Bong Go (Source not specified)	47	15%
Mean = 1.85 (Very Low Ability)		

Note: Frequency (f); Percentage (%); Level of Ability; 5 - Very High Ability; 4 - High Ability; 3 - Moderate Ability; 2- Low Ability; 0-1 - Very Low Ability

In Table 2.2, respondents performed best in identifying disinformation in the item “Conflicting Narratives Emerge Amid Flood Control Corruption Controversy”, with 210 correct responses or 67%, indicating the highest actual ability among the items. Conversely, they performed poorest on “Wency Cornejo Raises Questions Following Plunder Charges vs. Duterte and Bong Go”, with only 47 correct responses or 15%, reflecting the lowest actual ability. Overall, the mean score of 1.85 indicates that respondents generally have a very low ability to accurately identify disinformation, suggesting a gap between perceived confidence and actual skill in detecting false or misleading information.

Table 2.3
Actual Ability in Identifying Malinformation (n=314)

Item Statement	Correct Answer	
	f	%
1. WJ Construction Exec Confirms Repair Work at Sen. Erwin Tulfo's Office Before Senate Probe (Daily Tribune, Sept. 18, 2025)	140	45%
2. Escudero Slams Kickback Allegations as 'Orchestrated Attack' Against Senate (ABS-CBN News, Sept. 25, 2025)	151	48%
3. Palace Denies Involvement in VP Sara Duterte Impeachment Trial (Daily Tribune, Apr. 24, 2025)	110	35%
4. Sept. 21 Marked as National Day of Protest, Commemorating Martial Law Anniversary (Showbiz News Update)	111	35%
5. Palace to China: Philippines 'No One's Chess Piece,' Defends Military Sovereignty (Daily Tribune, Mar. 27, 2025)	172	55%
Mean = 2.18 (Low Ability)		

Note: Frequency (f); Percentage (%); Level of Ability; 5 - Very High Ability; 4 - High Ability; 3 - Moderate Ability; 2- Low Ability; 0-1 - Very Low Ability

In Table 2.3, respondents showed the highest ability in identifying the item “Palace to China: Philippines ‘No One’s Chess Piece,’ Defends Military Sovereignty” with 55% answering correctly, indicating relatively better recognition of malinformation in political or national security contexts. The lowest ability was observed in identifying “Palace Denies Involvement in VP Sara Duterte Impeachment Trial” and “Sept. 21 Marked as National Day of Protest, Commemorating Martial Law Anniversary,” with only 35% answering correctly, reflecting difficulty in detecting malinformation related to political events and historical commemorations. Overall, the mean score of 2.18 indicates that respondents have a low ability to identify malinformation, suggesting a need for enhanced skills in recognizing misleading or harmful content online.

DISCUSSION

Confidence in Identifying Fake News

The high confidence ratings across misinformation, disinformation, and malinformation indicate that freshmen students perceive themselves as capable of evaluating online information. This result is consistent with findings by Hopp (2021) and Paciello et al. (2023), who reported that higher self-efficacy is associated with stronger perceived ability in detecting fake news. Similar to the observations of Corbu et al. (2020) and Martínez-Costa et al. (2022), students in the present study may exhibit a “nobody-fools-me” perception, wherein they believe they are less vulnerable to fake news than others. Local studies by Linsangan et al. (2021) and Fajardo (2023) further support this result, showing that Filipino students often express high confidence in identifying fake news despite limited evaluative training.

Actual Ability in Identifying Fake News

Despite high confidence, students demonstrated low to very low actual ability, particularly in identifying disinformation. This finding aligns with international studies by Thompson et al. (2022) and Kim et al. (2021), which emphasize that fake news detection requires advanced analytical reasoning and verification skills that many students lack. Locally, Fajardo (2023) and Maningo et al. (2022) similarly found that Filipino students' actual competencies in fact-checking and contextual evaluation remain low, even with high social media exposure. The difficulty in identifying disinformation reflects findings by Nascimento (2025) and Dabbous et al. (2021), who noted that deliberately deceptive and emotionally framed content significantly reduces detection accuracy.

Overall Interpretation of Findings

Overall, the results reinforce conclusions drawn in both international and local literature that a persistent confidence–competence gap exists among students. Consistent with Hopp (2021), Corbu et al. (2020), and Fajardo (2023), freshmen students tend to overestimate their ability to identify fake news while demonstrating limited actual performance, especially in detecting disinformation. These findings underscore the need for targeted media and information literacy interventions that emphasize critical evaluation, contextual understanding, and verification practices to better align perceived confidence with actual ability.

Conclusions

Confidence alone is not a reliable indicator of one's ability to identify fake news. Although students believe they can recognize false information, their limited actual ability to discern fake news shows that awareness without proper analytical training is insufficient. This implies that educational institutions should not only promote confidence but also provide structured opportunities for students to practice critical evaluation and verification of information. Ultimately, the findings emphasize the need to bridge the gap between perception and competence to cultivate discerning, reflective, and responsible media users in an age where fake news is increasingly prevalent.

Recommendations

In light of the findings of the study, the following recommendations are proposed for the university administrators and academic units concerned:

1. Develop and integrate a structured Media and Information Literacy (MIL) component into general education courses to address the gap between students' confidence and actual ability in identifying fake news.
2. Encourage faculty members to incorporate guided fact-checking activities, case analyses, and real-world examples of misinformation, disinformation, and malinformation in classroom instruction.
3. Provide students with access to verified digital resources and tools that support

information verification and critical evaluation of online content.

4. Conduct periodic assessments and feedback mechanisms to monitor students' progress in fake news identification and to support continuous improvement of instructional strategies.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

To uphold the principles of sound and responsible research, this study adhered to established ethical standards. Ethical clearance was sought from Foundation University to secure permission to conduct the study among the target population.

Before the conduct of the study, informed consent was obtained by clearly explaining the study's purpose, scope, and terms of participation, emphasizing that participation was voluntary and that respondents could withdraw at any time without penalty; all research instruments were also reviewed and approved by qualified experts to ensure ethical compliance. During data collection, confidentiality and anonymity were strictly observed, questionnaires were administered with clear explanations of the study's objectives, and respondents were assured that their identities would remain confidential to encourage honest and voluntary participation. After data collection, responses were encoded, organized, and analyzed using Microsoft Excel and JAMOVI, with all identifying information removed, and the data securely stored and used solely for academic and research purposes.

In compliance with the Ethics Committee of Foundation University, all required protocols were followed to ensure the study's ethical soundness. The researchers maintained a professional, neutral stance throughout data collection and reporting to prevent bias or judgment. Additionally, the researchers declared the use of OpenAI's GPT-4 and QuillBot as tools to enhance the readability and clarity of this manuscript. After using these tools, the authors carefully reviewed, revised, and validated the content, taking full responsibility for its accuracy and integrity.

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